

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract

The issue of gender equality has been actively studied in the last decade. Islamic countries attract special attention, as they lag behind in ensuring women's rights. In this study, the researcher draws attention to how and to what extent globalization has affected the development of equality between men and women in Saudi Arabia, a country that has relatively recently begun to consider women's rights. The article lists the reforms that have been introduced over the past 10 years, as well as studied the problems that require the attention of the authorities and immediate solutions.

Key words: Gender equality, gender policy, human rights, globalization, culture, religion, law, Sharia, gender gap, education, politics

Globalization is a process of worldwide economic, political, cultural and religious integration and unification. It has affected every aspect of our lives, but in this study we would like to focus on its impact on gender equality, particularly in Saudi Arabia. Globalization requires equality between men and women in education, work, freedom of speech and other human rights

Saudi Arabia is one of those countries that is a symbol of gender inequality. In 2021, it ranked 147 out of 156 on the Gender Gap Index list. However, despite the current strict prohibitions, several new laws in recent years have allowed women to breathe a little more freely. We tell you what rights women have received in one of the most gender-unjust countries in the world.

Even 40 years ago, women in Saudi Arabia could drive cars, communicate with strangers, and not wear traditional clothes. Nevertheless, in 1979, two significant events took place in the Middle East that determined the future of the country. First,

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there was the Islamic revolution in Iran - the monarchy fell, all relations with the West stopped. This event prompted many Islamic countries to think about changing the course of government in the direction of strengthening the clergy. Then, at the end of the same year, a terrorist attack occurred in the holy city of Mecca, which is located in Saudi Arabia. 255 pilgrims became victims. Thus, the terrorists wanted to force the authorities to break off relations with the West and return to traditions. And they succeeded.¹

Saudi Arabia has become a conservative Islamic state. Sharia laws began to operate there, causing amazement in a person brought up in European values. This could not but affect the position of women. They were not only dressed in abayas - black robes that cover the whole body. They were forbidden to work and study, because the main mission of a woman is to take care of the house, give birth and raise children. The situation with women's rights in Saudi Arabia is changing, albeit very slowly. Taking Western women as an example, Saudi women are demanding equal rights in matters of work, education, social status, the right to travel unaccompanied, the right to drive cars, etc. Over the past decade, they have gained rights and freedoms that only 20 years ago they could only dream.¹

Saudi Arabia is an absolute monarchy with an advisory council (Majlis ash-Shura) whose legislators are appointed by the king. Previously, only men over 30 could hold positions there. The turning point of the situation occurred in 2013: for the first time, women also entered the council by decree of King Abdullah, taking 30 seats. Three of them were appointed deputy chairpersons of the committees on health and environmental protection, on human rights and petitions, as well as on the information and cultural committee.

Two years later, the king gave women yet another political freedom. For the first time, they were allowed to vote and stand for election. At that time, more than 900 women across the country applied for participation in the elections. Some Saudi

¹ A. Al-Mohamed. Saudi Women's Rights: Stuck at a Red Light. Arab Insight. 2008, 2 (1): 45-51. Retrieved November 28, 2011 from www.arabinsight.com.

women are not afraid to fight for change in the lives of their compatriots. Thus, businesswoman Lubna Olayan called for the abolition of gender separation in business. And when hiring an employee, consider his qualifications, not gender. Olayan herself has achieved tremendous success in her career. In 2015, she was included in the Forbes list of 100 most influential women, and in 2018 she became the first woman in the country to head a major financial institution - a bank.

Contrary to prevailing stereotypes, Sharia allows women to build a career. But only with the consent of the husband and the condition that the work does not harm family responsibilities. Also, a woman can work if she is left without a breadwinner. In Saudi Arabia, until 2005, women could only work in a limited number of areas, such as medicine, education, and commerce. At the same time, they can work only in those places that are visited exclusively by women.

Perhaps one of the most significant achievements of women's freedom in Saudi Arabia is the ability to leave the house without a male escort. All women in the country must have a male guardian - father, brother, husband or uncle. Until recently, guardians had complete control over women's lives. Without their consent, they could not leave the house, get a job, open a bank account. And this is only a small part of the list of what you need to get permission for.

In 2021, women in Saudi Arabia were allowed to serve in the military. To do this, they must be citizens of the country with a secondary education, not younger than 21 years old and not older than 40 years old. And also not lower than 1.55 meters and without civil service behind them. If the requirements are met, the woman is free to apply for military service. She can become a soldier, lance corporal, corporal, sergeant and master sergeant. In September 2021, the first group of women soldiers graduated from the Women's Training Center of the Saudi Arabian Armed Forces. And in March 2022, the Ministry of the Interior of Saudi Arabia opened an admission for women who want to serve in the border troops.

In June 2021, Saudi Arabia introduced an amendment to the law that allowed adult women to live in a separate house without the permission of a guardian. This applies to widows, and unmarried, and divorced. Previously, women who lost their husbands

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were required to return to the guardian's home. And unmarried people could not live separately until marriage. Now guardians will not be able to report to the police if an unmarried adult woman decides to live separately. The text of the amendment also states that if a woman is sentenced to prison, she will not be transferred to a guardian at the end of her term.

Of course, if we proceed from the values of the 21st century, all these changes are not so significant, and the measures, according to representatives of human rights organizations, are completely half-hearted. There is still a lot of work ahead, but even if you compare modern Saudi Arabia with what it was 20 years ago, it is clear that a lot has been done.

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